

THE APPEARANCE OF BORROWED ABBREVIATIONS AND THEIR SCOPE OF USE IN THE RUSSIAN LANGUAGE

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Abstract: The relevance of the research is determined by the frequent use of abbreviation vocabulary and a developed system of abbreviation models in modern foreign languages; the appearance of a significant number of new abbreviations, which are often key formations for a certain period of time and predetermine the mobility and openness of the abbreviation microsystem; the specifics of the use of analyzed units in various types of discourse in the absence of a comprehensive, generalizing study of abbreviation in modern foreign languages.

Key words: Russian language, methodology, Russian vocabulary, intercultural communication, analysis, structure, abbreviation, communicative relevance, foreign languages, terms.

Russian vocabulary has always been one of the most active processes of vocabulary replenishment. N.M. Shansky, a well-known linguist, defines borrowing as "any word that came into the Russian language from the outside, even if it does not differ in its morphemes from native Russian words" Varieties of using borrowed abbreviations in English and Russian: Materials of the inter-university. conf. "Topical issues of philology. Theory and methodology of teaching foreign languages".

The main reasons for the penetration of Anglicisms into the Russian language are the diplomatic and trade relations between Russia and England, which began in the XVI century. Along with these reasons, we can distinguish other ones that are characteristic of the Russian language already in modern reality:

1. The emergence of the names of a new reality, a new subject, a new concept that has appeared in public life. For example: publicity, brand, snob, humor, player, bulldozer, cocktail. Due to the spread of American science fiction films in Russia, two Anglicisms appeared in the Russian language: cyborgization (cyborgization - the replacement of individual human organs with cybernetic devices as a scientific and technical problem) and cyborg (cyborg - a person subjected to cyborgization).

2. The appearance of a new word, which is a more convenient designation of what was previously called using the phrase: the most sold book is a bestseller, a

sharpshooter is a sniper, a short-distance runner is a sprinter, a hotel for motorists is a motel, entrepreneurial activity is a business, one of the best works of a composer or performer who has visited the hit- the parade is a hit. The anglicisms zapper (zapper - a person who endlessly switches TV channels) and zapping (the process of switching) are also designed to replace descriptive Russian phrases. The Anglicism of the quiz replaces the descriptive phrase "a radio or television game of questions and answers on various topics with prizes."

3. The absence of a corresponding concept in the cognitive base of the receptor language. Such anglicisms as badge, classifier, laptop and its new varieties: audiobook and powerbook; organizer, pager and tweager, canvas, timer, beeper, scrambler, intercom, shredder, overhead, plotter, scanner, tuner, toner, pack, etc. have firmly entered the dictionary of a business person of the 90s.

4. New words that arose as a result of the need to emphasize a partial change in the social role of the subject in a changing society: office - office, office space, Sberbank - before the savings bank.

5. The influence of foreign culture, which is dictated simply by the fashion for English words. At the time of Pushkin, it was considered a rule of good form to speak French, today - in English.

Accordingly, the merchant alternately becomes a merchant, then a businessman, and the person dealing the cards is a dealer, then a dealer. Most of these words, due to their relevance, very quickly became common and entered the active vocabulary.

6. Clarification or detailing of the relevant concept. For example, in the Russian language there was a word jam, which was called both liquid and thick jam. To distinguish thick jam from fruits or berries, which is a homogeneous mass, from liquid, in which whole berries could be preserved, thick jam began to be called the English word jam.

These reasons for the penetration of Anglicisms into the Russian language are extralinguistic, external. According to L.P. Krysin, a recognized researcher of foreign language vocabulary, and in particular Anglicisms, there are also a number of internal reasons for Krysin L.P. Among them: the need to differentiate concepts or to specialize them (installation, French. installation 'installation, equipment') is a word that appeared to denote a new type of works of fine art, thereby it would have to fall into the first group of foreign language vocabulary; however, the main reason for its appearance in the language was the need to distinguish this kind of work, on the one hand, from planar (paintings, etchings, prints, etc. on the other hand, from voluminous, but having a fundamentally different character (sculptures), since the installation involves the use of various kinds of household items, machine parts, appliances, etc. as material.); the presence of established systems of terms in the language, more or less homogeneous in their source of origin (terminology of

computer technology, which has developed on the basis of the English language: website, banner, browser), and some socio-psychological reasons: the prestige of a foreign language word (exclusive instead of exclusive), the communicative relevance of the concept and the corresponding word (drug addiction, drug trafficking, mafia, racketeering, racketeers, etc.).

The intensity of borrowings from the XVI century, (when Anglicisms penetrated only into narrow spheres of life, namely, the spheres of artillery and ship specification) and before the processes in modern Russian (when borrowings penetrate almost all spheres of human activity) are changing at a noticeably accelerating pace.

All borrowed words are combined into several thematic groups, including:

- economic terms (roaming - "distribution; possibility to roam - "to wander, to wander" and other modern concepts such as: discount, tender, clearing, manager, marketing, branding, franchising, franchise, leasing, monitoring, merchandiser, warrant, quotation, lockout, preferential benefits, licensor's know-how, brokerage operations, consignment operations, on-call transaction, option, bonus deduction, bank located in an offshore financial center, hedger, stock market, goodwill, consolidated budget, solidary);

- political terms (speaker - chairman of Parliament, from the English speaker - "speaker" and "chairman of the House of Commons in England and the House of Representatives in the USA"; inauguration - "inauguration ceremony of the president of the country", from the English inauguration "taking office"; mayor, vice mayor, prefect, sub-prefect; administration, press attache, press conference, press release, briefing);

- computer technologies (site - from English site - "location, location", file - from English file - "registrar; dossier, case; submission of any document", etc.);⁵⁸

- sports vocabulary (fitness - from the English fitness - "compliance" (from to be fit - "fit, be in shape", etc.), skateboard - "skating on a board with rollers", from the English skate - "skating, sliding" and board - "board"; snowboarding - "riding on a board in the snow", from the English snow

- "snow" and board - "board"; snowblade - "riding on snow on large-sized stunt skis", from the English snowblade - "stunt skis"; biker - "cyclist; motorcyclist", from the English bike - abbreviated, razg. from bicycle - "bicycle"; shaping - from the English. shaping - "shaping" (from to shape - "to shape"));

- names of objects and realities of everyday life (shaker - from English shaker - "a vessel for making cocktails" (from to shake - "shake"), toaster - from English toaster - "a device for toasting toast" (from toast - "toasted slice of bread, toast"); roaster - from English. roaster - "brazier" (from to roast "to fry"), etc.);

- names of cultural phenomena, in particular in the musical sphere (single - "a song recorded separately", from the English single - "one, only", remake (remake) - "remake", from the English remake in the same meaning; image - "image", from the English image "image, image"; design - "design" from the English design - "idea, plan; design";

- "poster, poster");

- names of professions and activities (security - "security", from the English security - "security, reliability; security, protection"; provider

- "supplier", from the English provider - with the same meaning; realtor - "real estate agent", from amer. realtor (from the English realty - "real estate"); broker - from the English broker - "commission agent, appraiser; person selling property"; killer - "professional killer", from the English killer - "killer" from to kill "to kill"; racketeer - "extortionist", from amer. racketeer - "participant in a fraudulent enterprise"; gangster, bandit - extortionist from amer. racket - "blackmail, extortion", etc.; handmaker - "that who is engaged in manual work", from the English hand - "hand" and make - "to do"; image maker - "the one who develops the image", from the English image - "image" and make - "to do"; merchandiser - "the one who is engaged in the design of trade shelves", from the English merchandise - "goods, trade", etc.);

- terms used in cosmetology (make-up - "makeup", from the English make-up - "makeup"; concealer, from the English concealer - "pencil corrector"; peeling - "facial cleansing", from the English peeling - "cleansing, cleaning", from to peel - "peel, peel; peel"; peeling cream

- peeling-cream - "cream that removes the top layer of skin"; lifting

- "lifting", from the English lifting - "lifting, lifting"; lifting cream - lifting-cream - "cream that tightens the skin"; vanish cream - vanish-cream

- "cream that removes capillary nets"; scrub - "cream for exfoliating, cleansing the skin", from the English to scrub - "scratch", etc.).59

Anglicisms are also often found in the language of newspapers, advertisements, and advertisements [3], which can be completely replaced by their Russian equivalents: second-hand - "used clothes", from the English second-hand:

- "second-hand, second-hand"; lunch (lunch) - from English lunch - "second breakfast"; teenager - from English teen-ager - "teenager, boy or girl from 13 to 18 years"; parking - from English parking - "parking"; sale - from sale - "sale at a reduced price at the end of the season"; minivan or minivan - "minibus", from English. van (abbreviated. from caravan) - "van", etc.

Getting into the language, the word goes through several stages of the so-called "Russification". M.I. Chernysheva, Doctor of Philology, specialist in lexicology and lexicography, identifies four such stages: penetration, proper borrowing, or entry of

the word into the language, assimilation and, finally, the rooting of the borrowed word in the recipient language, i.e. in the borrowing language, the problem of reduction in languages: A collection of abstracts of the XIII International Scientific Conference of students, postgraduates and young scientists "Lomonosov". M., 2006. pp. 90-93.. At each stage, the word undergoes partial or numerous changes that force the foreign language word to adapt according to the norms of the recipient's language.

Now there is a process of actively replenishing the vocabulary of the Russian language with foreign-language abbreviated innovations.

During the transition of abbreviations from the donor language to the recipient language, various adaptation processes occur. The analysis of the material allows us to identify the following specific groups.

Graphic mastering of a borrowed abbreviation is its transmission in writing by means of the Russian alphabet: AA > American Army, AA > American Army; BBC > British Broadcasting Corporation and BBC > British Broadcasting Corporation.

The lexically mastered word obeys the lexico-semantic system of the language: PC > Personal computer and PC > Personal Computer; IIHF > International ice hockey Federation and IIHF > International Ice Hockey Federation.

Recently, foreign-language abbreviations have shown quite high derivational activity: a foreign-language word, acting as a producer, has become included in a certain word-formation paradigm: SPA/SPA: SPA salon, SPA procedure; SMS/SMS: SMS message, SMS search, SMS dating, SMS announcement, SMS-slang, text, text, etc.

This group includes the following abbreviations: GPS: GPS receiver, GPS device, GPS set, IP: IP telephony, IP address.

As you know, fully mastered, borrowed, abbreviations are abbreviations adapted to the graphic, word-formation, lexical, grammatical levels of the Russian language: VIP - Very important person and VIP, VIP "especially important person" / VIP, VIP / VIP banking, VIP ticket, VIP guest VIP lounge, VIP, VIP, etc.

CM - Corresponding Member "corresponding member", RAM - Random Access Memory "Computer RAM".

Russian research allows us to talk about the activation of foreign-language abbreviations in the Russian language, which in one way or another tend to enter the Russian language system.

Fully mastered foreign language words (borrowings) are contrasted with words that are not developed by the system of the borrowing language-barbarisms. Between them there are exotisms - words mastered graphically, word-formatively, grammatically, but not mastered lexically.

The considered material allowed, thus, to detail the specified classification, having allocated, along with borrowings and barbarisms, intermediate groups. In

addition, along with lexical exotisms, according to our research, a new type of foreign language words of this group can be distinguished - grammatical exotisms, words mastered graphically, word-formatively, lexically, but not mastered grammatically.

The influx of Anglicisms over the past 5-10 years is very large. This indicates an increasing need to name new phenomena, objects, discoveries, the development of relations and ties between Russia, England, America, as well as the prestige of the English language.

The historical situation at the end of the XX century is extremely favorable for the development of contacts with foreign countries, and linguistically this has affected the increase in borrowings. The fashion for English words should be attributed to factors of a different, negative nature. The penetration and influence of borrowings on the language is, on the one hand, a natural phenomenon, reflecting the economic, political, cultural, social ties and relations between Russia and other countries, in particular with America, that have intensified in the last decade. On the other hand, it can be noted that in the pursuit of everything foreign, in an effort to copy Western patterns, we are increasingly losing our identity, including in language, because language reflects the way of life and thoughts. However, this is an unavoidable phenomenon, and therefore it is worth studying regardless of what impact it has.

Language as one of the most important components of national culture, as a reflection of the national identity of the people, cannot remain aloof from these processes. Language changes are necessary consequences of our way of using language, representing a "special case of socio-cultural changes". The problem of borrowing is relevant in a constantly changing world. Borrowing lexical elements from one language to another is a very ancient phenomenon and is already known to the languages of the ancient world. For the fate of borrowed words in a new language for them, the way in which they penetrated into this language has a certain meaning. Abbreviation is a part of borrowings and as a way of word formation is a complex, multifaceted phenomenon rooted in the distant past. Its appearance is due to both extralinguistic reasons and linguistic reasons. One of the most active processes of replenishment of the vocabulary of the Russian language has always been the borrowing of words of foreign vocabulary. The intensity of borrowings from the XVI century . and the number of processes in modern Russian is changing at a noticeably accelerating pace. The main areas of distribution of borrowed abbreviations are political discourses, newspaper publications, publications on the Internet and the press. Now there is a process of actively replenishing the vocabulary of the Russian language with foreign-language abbreviated innovations. All these phenomena are

formed due to close cooperation with European countries and the exchange of information.

In English, the percentage of borrowings is much higher than in many other languages, because for historical reasons it turned out to be, in contrast to, for example, Icelandic, very permeable. The English language, more than any other language, had the opportunity to borrow foreign words in conditions of direct contact: first in the Middle Ages from foreign invaders who succeeded each other in the British Isles, and later in the conditions of trade expansion and colonization activity of the British themselves.

In modern English, there are abbreviations borrowed from various languages. With a natural connection between the meaning of a word and its sound, it is said that there is phonetic motivation.

The peculiarity of the current borrowings also consists in an extremely high frequency of use, as a result of which their novelty is erased very soon and most borrowings enter the circle of common vocabulary a short time after their appearance. The main function implemented by abbreviations is evaluation based on certain techniques of language play. At the same time, evaluative borrowed abbreviations intensively increase the evaluative potential, demonstrating a distinct dynamics of various types within the word-formation forms formed by them.

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